

FIDDL: EVALUATION OF A SMARTPHONE BASED APPLICATION DESIGNED FOR A MUSIC WORKSHOP FOR CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

Introducing music training to children can often present challenges, so alternative methods and tools different from traditional training are desirable. In this paper we describe the design and evaluation of an application for musical performance and playful expression targeted to children age 7-11. The application is tailored to fit into the context of a musical workshop named Small Composers, which is run by the FIGURA Ensemble. The application was evaluated in an actual workshop setting to assess how well it can be integrated into the conventional session, and it was found to have potential for being part of future workshops.

1. INTRODUCTION

Children are known to have exceptional creativity and imagination, which can manifest in various activities. The fostering of this creativity has been approached in various fields. However, introducing music training can often pose difficulties at a young age. The learning curve of musical instruments, together with complex musical principles and notation, are highlighting the need for alternative tools and methods. Different educational aids, programs and workshops are addressing this issue, seeking new ways to involve children into music composition and performance [1].

The Copenhagen based musical collective Figura ensemble runs a successful workshop called Small Composers [2]. The workshop combines professional musical work and education, focusing on developing fundamental musical skills for children with no necessary prior experience. Their main goal is to stimulate creativity, encourage children to play and compose music, and deepen their musical understanding through various exercises. Collaboration, experimentation and playful musical expression are playing a central role in the definition of Small Composers [2]. Figura's call for collaborators and their modern pedagogical approach, shows as a potential context for introducing novel music technology.

The collaboration with Figura and the integration of music technology to their workshop has already showed po-

tential with the success of a workshop which took place during the 2017 edition of the New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME) conference. This one day workshop was a collaboration with composer and instrument maker Troy Rogers [3]. The workshop included building and programming a simple robot, and the composition and performance of a collaborative musical piece. The event received positive feedback from both the participants and the organizers, and opened up for future collaborations.

The goal of this study is to design and develop a complementary tool, to aid Figura ensemble's workshop, focusing on music performance for novices and non-musicians. Instead of an educational tool, the aim is to engage children into the activities of the workshop and encourage experimentation, rewarding curiosity and creativity.

2. RELATED WORK

Similarly to Figura's Small Composers, MIT Media Lab's project, Toy Symphony [4], was aiming to introduce music for children through creative activities and the involvement of professional musicians. As a central part, it combined traditional resources with a set of novel instruments, known as music toys. Music toys consisted of three instruments, the 'Beat Bugs', the 'Music Shapers' and 'Hyperscore'. The 'Beat Bugs' are a set of handheld, percussion instruments, and the 'Shapers' are designed to manipulate the sound of conventional instruments real-time. Both of these tangible interfaces are designed for collaborative performances, while 'Hyperscore' [5] [4] is a software tool, designed to facilitate music composition for children through visual analogies. Each series of workshops ends with a concert featuring the rehearsed performances of the children and their compositions played by an ensemble. Informal observations indicated numerous benefits regarding musical understanding, and verified the potential of technology aided musical activities. This alternative approach not only eases the learning curve for exploring music at an early age, but also suggests a different route for learning music [1] [4].

A more recent study addressing a similar topic, EnseWing, uses sensor technology to aid collaborative musical performances of children. The interaction is based mainly on embodied metaphors, and it focuses on emulating a musical ensemble. Members of the ensemble have to use hand gestures to control different tone parameters, and they are also

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provided with a graphical user interface conveying feedback about the performance. Field study showed that the embodied music control is easy to grasp and children are able to reproduce such gestures easily [6].

A more educational, yet similar approach has been presented by Mogclass, a collaborative music environment designed for classrooms. The setup consists of a network of mobile devices where each group of students are connected via headphones. The project received positive feedback from teachers and students alike, implying future studies in interactive classroom technologies and alternative methods for music classes for children [7].

Toy symphony highlighted the importance of a design which is not too complicated for beginners, but also offers depth for musical expression. EnseWing suggests embodied interactions for a performance oriented perspective, due to the ease of learning. Mogclass promotes the benefits of mobile based applications, and the importance of diverse interactions and musical outputs. There are empirical design solutions in such a multi layered scenario, promoting an iterative design process, tailored for chosen context and target group. To generalize, software implementations are giving more flexibility and better means for distribution, which is important from both a commercial and a practical perspective. The current state of mobile technology renders smartphones as powerful tools for computation, communication, and interaction through modern sensor technology.

Music software often requires the control of multiple interdependent parameters at the same time. A study on real-time sound sculpting with hand gestures, highlighted the potential behind our ability to produce accurate, well articulated movements with our hands, and its suitability for complex mapping schemes [8]. Interaction by gestures with digital media can be commonly seen in smartphones, utilizing a touchscreen or other sensor technology. Gestures and connection between gestures and sounds are thoroughly investigated in musical research as well, due to their expressive quality, although few empirical solutions were discovered on the mapping of gestures to sound [9, 10]. The translation of physical gestures to expressive control parameters is at the heart of designing new instruments. In such real-time systems, gestures and sounds are both temporal processes, therefore, instantaneous, responsive changes are expected [9].

The use of musical analogies is believed to serve as a complementary aspect on designing interactions for new a musical interface. Musical analogies are closely related to the theory of image schemas, which are building blocks of conceptual metaphors. Image schemas represent patterns of embodied experiences and their perception, and it has been discovered that musical and other abstract concepts are rooted in such prior sensory-motor experiences. This suggest that an interface can be considered intuitive if the user can subconsciously utilize actions based on these prior experiences during interactions, and the parameters are altered according to their expectations [11]. Research indicates that changes in musical parameters are associ-

ated with images of motion. Static visual attributes such as size, height, shape are also interplay with the perception of auditory parameters [12]. The relationship between pitch and vertical dimension is equally present in musicians and non-musicians [12] [11]. The relationship between speed and tempo, and proximity and loudness also well grounded in listener's experiences [12]. Studies concluded, that such musical space is not perfectly symmetrical and linear, as the direction of change is also influencing the strength of certain musical-spatial analogies [12] [13].

There are also numerous commercially available music apps on the market for children, both with educational and creative purposes. However, they are not satisfying all the demands of Small Composers. Most popular apps designed for children are focusing on composition, with sequencing or toggling sounds or loops, which does not align with the workshop's activities. Performance oriented applications are mostly mimicking real instruments, not allowing a wide range of timbral variations. Music apps, designed for an older target group are often providing an overwhelming set of features posing a steep learning curve, and those with primary focus on sampling are lacking expressive control.

3. SMALL COMPOSERS

In order to establish the design requirements we interviewed the conductor of the workshop, Peter Bruun, who is also a co-author of this paper. Peter works as a professional composer and he has been in charge of managing and developing the workshop for the past 13 years. Small composers' workshops motivate storytelling through sound. Such workshops are usually involving 20-25 children of age 7-11, who are forming smaller groups for the course of the activities. Most of the times the workshop takes place at a school's classroom. The children are asked to bring musical artifacts or simple instruments from home, but they are also provided with some. Listening exercises are forming the basis for acquiring the ability to describe sounds, both verbally and through visual analogies. Instead of traditional notation, children learn to compose rhythmic and melodic figures, through storytelling, and the illustration of the sound scenery. The stories serve as a way to conceptualize music and to render meaning to sounds and motives. They also allow children to use their imagination, as an incentive to tap into their creativity. These concepts also facilitate replicability, which receives great emphasis in learning and performing music. Peter highlights the importance of being able to produce a wide variety of sounds in an expressive manner, which helps to act out the stories. During the workshop, children are encouraged to share their ideas and compositions with others, teaching them to evaluate artistic quality. The final sessions ends with a concert, where each group is performing their composition as an ensemble. Small composers is a well developed real-life concept, giving great opportunity to investigate the impact of music technology on alternative teaching methods.

4. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

Our design is primarily based on five main elements: intuitiveness to support novices, responsiveness for the performance oriented aspect, expressiveness to provide a greater sense of autonomy, wide variety of output to encourage exploration and replicability to help learning.

The accessibility and versatility of smartphones suggest the targeting of mobile platforms. The application was developed for iOS, and is distributed through the App Store. The application is referred to by the name 'Fiddl' [14]. 'Fiddl' was developed using the cross-platform C++ application framework 'JUICE' [15].

The foundation of 'Fiddl' is the ability to record short sound samples and play them back by utilizing touch gestures. The user's interactions can be seen in Figure 1. These interactions are manipulating the recorded sounds real-time, with audio parameters being mapped to the different gestures, and spatial information, such as screen coordinates. 'Fiddl' should encourage the sonic exploration via expressive touch gestures and turn everyday sounds into musical building blocks. In the workshop the children are using simple instruments. For 'Fiddl' to be well-integrated into the workshop, it should have the same role as these simple instruments, e.g. adding a sonified element to the story.

Figure 1. The use case diagram shows every possible user interaction and how the application generally responds to the user's actions.

By providing a limited set of interfaced parameters and simple touch gestures, the users should be able to engage, without any prior learning process, while being offered creative freedom and being able to produce a wide spectrum of output, through sample manipulation with touch gestures. The gestures should allow the users to learn patterns, to be able to recreate sounds, which they explored

through experimentation. The application requires real-time interaction, actively engaging the user. In order to be able to produce both rhythmic and sustained sounds the application features three main parameter spaces which the user can switch between, distinguished both in the nature of interactions and available sound transformations.

4.1 Interface Design and Mapping

The interface of the application (Figure 2,A) consists of two main areas: the recording area and a playback area. Additionally, there are three buttons, that allow the user to change between three main parameter spaces: sustained, impulse and discrete.

Figure 2. A: The initial interface when loading 'Fiddl' is the sustained space. 1) Recording Area: the user presses in the bottom field to record a sound of maximum 3 seconds. 2) Playback Area: The user can play a recorded sound by pressing/swiping somewhere in the playback area. 3) Parameter Spaces: The user can choose between three different parameters spaces. B: The interface while recording

An overview of the mappings for each parameter space can be seen in Table 1. This table shows how the gesture parameters, which are variables that are extracted from the raw touch data in the playback area, are mapped to audio parameters, which are variables that control the audio effect parameters which transform the output of the sound. The 'Parameter Space' column indicates which mapping is active when. The 'Gesture Parameter' column shows what variables are being extracted as a result of the users interactions in the playback area. These variables are mapped to parameters for audio filters and effects.

4.1.1 Record Button

To record a sound the user presses and holds on the area shown in Figure 2. The recording will last as long as the user holds a finger down in recording area (see Figure 2, B), or until the recording reaches three seconds in length. The beginning and end portion of the recorded audio is then truncated according to an amplitude threshold, to automatically crop the recording to a desired sample. The user can store only one recording at a time, so every time a

Parameter Space	Gesture Parameter	Audio Parameter	Mapping
Sustain Finger	x position	bandpass cutoff fc	$+x = +fc$
	y position	bandpass quality Q	$+y = +q$
	velocity v	envelope release time ert	$+v = +ert$
Sustain Fingers	y position	pitch p	$+y = +p$
	pinch distance pd	lowpass cutoff fc	$+pd = +fc$
		lowpass quality Q	$+pd = +q$
velocity v	envelope release time ert	$+v = +ert$	
Discrete Pitch	x position	bandpass cutoff fc	$+x = +fc$
	y position	discrete pitch dp	$+y = +dp$
Impulse	absolute distance ad	pitch p	$+ad = +p$
		highpass cutoff fc	$+ad = +fc$
		highpass quality Q	$+ad = +q$
		envelope release time ert	$+ad = -ert$
		reverb damping rd	$+ad = +rd$

Table 1. Overview of the mappings between gesture parameters and audio parameters in the different spaces. The mapping cell indicates how the parameters are related. E.g. $+x = +fc$ means that an increase in x , will mean an increase in the cutoff frequency fc .

new recording is made the previous recording is overwritten.

4.1.2 Playback Area

To play back the sound, the user has to interact with the playback area (Figure 2, A). Depending on the chosen parameter space, the sound will be manipulated according to how the user interacts in the playback area.

4.1.3 Sustained Space

The sustained space (Figure 3, C) gives the user two different options of interaction and sound output. The intention behind this space is that the user should record sounds of longer duration, and play them back by swiping across the playback area, which manipulates the audio parameters dynamically (Figure 3, C). When swiping across the screen with one finger, the finger position and swipe gesture parameters are used to produce different audio output. A trail is drawn as visual feedback (Figure 3, C). The horizontal and vertical finger location and swipe velocity are tracked and stored in the x , y , and velocity gesture parameters, respectively. Table 1 shows the detailed gesture parameter to audio parameter mappings for the sustain space. The

Figure 3. C: Graphical trail while playing sound in sustained space with 1 finger. D: 2 fingers added in sustained space. E: Discrete Space. F: Impulse Space.

faster the user swipes the finger, the more they increase their swipe velocity. An increase in swipe velocity will cause the sounds to be sustained for a longer period of time. When using two fingers, the user can control the size of a circle (Figure 3, D). The size of the circle and its vertical position are mapped to filter parameters. The vertical location, distance between two fingers, and swipe velocity are tracked and stored in the y , pinch distance, and velocity gesture parameters, respectively.

4.1.4 Discrete pitch space

While in sustained space, the user can reach the discrete space (3, E). Here a range of keys are presented, which are pitch-shifting the input sound following the pentatonic scale. The intention of this space is for the user to record periodic sounds and then play simple melodies. The horizontal and vertical finger locations are stored in the x and y variables, which are then mapped to the cutoff frequency of a bandpass filter and a discrete frequency, respectively. This space is arranged horizontally into distinct areas. As the user traverses from the bottom to the top of each area in the space, there is a corresponding discrete raise in the pitch of the sound. Left to right finger movement on each discrete area corresponds to the sound being filtered with a raise in the bandpass cutoff frequency.

4.1.5 Impulse Space

The impulse space (Figure 3, F) presents a different layout. Here the distance from the middle of the screen is mapped to various audio effect parameters. The intention of this space is for the user to record short sounds associated with percussive sounds, and play them by simply tapping somewhere in the playback area. The mappings are implemented to somewhat mimic a membrane instrument. Thereby when tapping close to the middle, the output audio will result in warmer sounds with longer decay. Moving away from the middle will cause the sounds to become increasingly brighter, more dampened, and higher pitched. The x and y finger location are obtained in order to calculate the position's absolute distance from the center. This absolute distance gesture parameter is then mapped as shown in Table 1.

5. TESTING FIDDL WITH CHILDREN

'Fiddl' was evaluated in a traditional workshop session. In the following we will describe the evaluation, motivated by the following research question:

Can a technological tool be integrated into the Figura ensemble workshop, such that it aids the outcome of the workshop in a positive way that engages the children into the activities of the workshop?

The research question was derived from the goal of the study, stated in the introduction, and to answer it a few success criteria were formed:

- The participants could successfully use the application, without any prior musical knowledge.
- The application adopted the same role as the other instruments/tools used in the workshop.
- The participants were able to perform using the application.

5.1 Setting

The workshop took place in Copenhagen in the elementary school *Skolen på Strandboulevarden*. The duration of the workshop was approximately six hours, with breaks included, corresponding to a normal day in school for the children. Three teachers were present to help manage the children.

5.2 Participants

45 children were present for the workshop, which is twice as much as the usual size of a Figura workshop. The classes were of 3rd grade elementary school, and the children were aged between 8-10. Most children were well practiced in the use of tablets as these are already an integrated part of their educational tools.

5.3 Procedure

The workshop was structured similarly to a traditional Small Composers workshop. As opposed to traditional Figura's

workshops, children would also be provided with an iPad, running 'Fiddl'.

After introducing the workshop (see Figure 4, left), and providing the participants with some examples on composing music with drawings and storytelling, the participants were divided into eleven groups of four children. A short introduction to the functionality of 'Fiddl' was given, after which the children were assigned to write their own composition based on a story. The participants were equipped with various instruments, as well as an iPad with 'Fiddl' installed. Each group had one iPad (see Figure 4, center). The groups were assigned to various locations on the school to avoid too much noise in the environment.

Once every group had finished their composition, they had to perform in front of a small audience consisting of pupils from lesser grades (see Figure 4, right).

Figure 4. Left: Composer Peter Bruun introduces the workshop. Middle: Children are using 'Fiddl' while composing. Right: A group performing their finished piece.

This study captured several forms of qualitative data: observations, open feedback from the participants and an interview with Peter Bruun. The purpose of the observations was to gather an idea of the overall usability of 'Fiddl' and identify technical issues. We were also interested in seeing how the participants cooperated to create the sounds, and if 'Fiddl' fit into the flow of the workshop. Each observer was given an observation sheet, listing guidelines for the areas of subject. Observers walked between groups and noted relevant behaviour. Based on the data gathered from the different observers, it was then possible to generate an overall idea of the main issues. After the final concert, the participants were gathered in a classroom. Here a short session of open feedback was held. The participants were asked what they thought of the workshop and 'Fiddl'. The participants were very open to give their opinion, and had many valuable ideas for future improvement. Finally, an interview with the composer Peter Bruun was held. This was necessary to completely understand how well the application was integrated, since it needs to serve as a complementary tool for both the children and the workshop conductors.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The qualitative analysis was based on thematic analysis of the observation notes, the open feedback from the kids, and the final interview with Peter Bruun.

6.1 Observations

6.1.1 Usability

The participants generally found it easy to use the application. They had little to no trouble with recording and playing sound. Initially, most participants did not understand that they needed to hold down on the playback area, rather than tapping, to play the whole sound. It also seemed intuitive for them to navigate between the different spaces. Most of them made an effort to explore the different spaces, but they mostly used the discrete pitch space. This space was also the simplest idea, and the participants interacted as we had intended. It also works well for almost any input sound, where other spaces requires more creative thinking regarding the input sound. Additionally the participants enjoyed the pitch modification. The other spaces did not get as much attention. Generally the participants tended to play the sound by holding the finger in a fixed position, which did not induce any dynamic sound manipulation. Therefore they did not experience the interesting aspect of the mapping and moved on to another space.

For the impulse space, the idea was that the user should record sounds of shorter duration, and play them back by tapping at various positions to hear how the sound was manipulated. In this case it was not clear to them that a certain input sound was expected. It seemed like they expected the output sound to be a longer sound, but the envelope was designed to cut off the sound rapidly. Almost all participants moved very quickly away from the impulse space, so we did not gather a significant amount of data for this space. Overall, the interface was intuitive and easy to use, but the mappings were not as clear as we would have hoped.

6.1.2 Context

This section focuses on the social interaction between the participants and how well the application fit into the workshop environment, and how well it worked as a tool for the composition assignment. In this test, we wanted to see if a single iPad was sufficient for one group, as the intention was that the iPad application should play the same role as other instruments in the workshop. The idea was that the application should work together with the acoustic instruments, rather than having a workshop solely consisting of iPads.

The participants approached the assignments in different ways and found various purposes for the application. For most groups, the application played a central role during the assignment. The iPad received a lot of attention from all group members, and everyone seemed eager to record something and try it out. In some cases the application seemed to distract the participants, removing focus from the actual assignment. However, after a while they all managed to create a composition, where both the application and the acoustic instruments had an equal role. There were some notable issues during the workshop.

Even though the groups had been separated to counter background noise in the recordings, the auto-truncation did not always work. This is because the groups were making noises during the recordings as well. Just a small sound

would be enough to be “classified” as valid recording. Therefore some recordings often had a small delay before the intended sound was played, which could lead to confusion and trouble when performing the sounds. The most frequent comments during the workshop regarded the possibility to record additional sounds and choose between them, and the possibility to save sounds. The restriction to one sound seemed to limit the creative use of the application. Some groups even acquired an additional iPad or iPhone to incorporate more sounds. The participants used the iPads with the built in speakers, which proved to be at a low sound level compared to the acoustic instruments and the environment. Some participants used external speakers and that showed an enhanced engagement with the app.

Only half of the groups actually performed using the application. This could simply because some groups did not see the purpose of using the recordings, when they could just simply perform sounds using acoustic instruments. The application was of course just provided as an optional tool. With this in mind, the other half of the groups successfully performed using both the application and acoustic instruments, and some groups even used multiple instances of the application using their own mobile devices.

6.2 Open Feedback

The comments from the participants pointed towards improvements for future development. The participants had a lot of comments, but in general they can all be summarized to the following: it should be possible to record multiple sounds, save them and choose between them. Additionally they noted that the iPad speakers were not loud enough. The rest of the comments regarded more complex functionality that would allow for composition within the application. But since the application is designed for performance, these comments were disregarded.

6.3 Interview

The first note was that the application worked differently from group to group.

“Some of the groups had definitely managed to integrate it somehow in their creation. And for others it seemed a little like it had been rather an obstacle”

This is a clear reference to the fact that half of the groups chose not to use the iPads for the final performance. Some of the children had found it inspiring, while it did not really work out for the others.

The issue might not necessarily lie on the application alone, but also the structure of the workshop:

“We had limited time for this workshop. We had to present them with two different things. We had to present them with the idea of making a piece of music using small sounds that they can make themselves and also introduce this application”

The participants did not get much practice time with the application. It was suggested, that this could have been an issue, indicating that the application might not be as intuitive as we had hoped. There were minor technical prob-

lems, which were mentioned as a reason for why some of the children did not use the application for the performance. Because it was simply not reliable enough. However, it was added that *"Had it worked, of course, technically perfect and had they had the time to play around with it a bit more, I think probably they would all have found a way to integrate it in an inspiring way in their creation"*. This indicated that, despite the technical flaws, the idea and concept of the application would fit well into the context of the workshop. The interview concluded, that there is potential for the application to be integrated as a tool for future workshop sessions. The combination of iPads and acoustic instruments was deemed to work well, as the children could also record the instruments and play them differently.

In the feedback session, some children had ideas that would take the application further, by adding new features. Although, the ones focusing on the compositional aspect, were disregarded, since they deviate from the general intention.

"I see that the main reason for why it actually works, and can be made to work in such a short time in this particular setting is that it is so simple, and that it does what it does in such a straightforward way".

6.4 Final Remarks

The participants could successfully use the application without any prior musical knowledge. An important note to make is that the majority of the children only used the discrete pitch space, which could be due to the fact that this space offered more drastic modifications to the input sound, and thereby was more entertaining to use. Another reason could be that they simply could not find a use for the audio manipulations applied in the other spaces.

Initially the application did receive more attention than the other musical artifacts in the groups, however after experimenting with different sounds and options it was more balanced. In some cases groups even combined the tools, by recording sounds generated from the acoustic artifacts. In the final performance there was a good balance between the use of the traditional instruments and the iPad.

This also concludes the third success criteria as the groups were able to use the application as part of their performance. However, half of the groups chose not to use the iPad for the performance.

Based on the final interview with Peter Bruun and the evaluation of the success criteria, it can be concluded that there is definitely a potential for the application to be well integrated into the Small Composers workshop. However, the evaluation pointed out some issues that needs to be resolved. These issues can be defined as design requirements for further development: it should be possible to record multiple sounds, save them and choose between them; it should be compatible with external speakers; some of the parameter spaces need to be re-imagined and possibly discarded.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper has documented the design and evaluation of a musical application. It was developed for a music workshop that traditionally uses only acoustic instruments. The application was designed with the active involvement of the conductor of the workshop. An evaluation was carried out in the real-life workshop setting, which proved the design's potential for a successful integration into the future sessions workshop.

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